

Photolytic and photocatalytic removal of a mixture of four veterinary antibiotics

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Abstract

The removal of a mixture of four veterinary antibiotics (VA) – tetracycline (TET), ciprofloxacin (CIP), sulfadiazine (SDZ) and sulfamethoxazole (SMX) – via photodegradation (UVC) and photocatalysis with TiO₂ (UVC/TiO₂) was investigated in a batch reactor under different initial concentrations (20, 100, 500 and 1000 µg/L per antibiotic). Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to a mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS) was used to determine the removal of these veterinary antibiotics. The removal of all antibiotics via photolysis was around 98 - 99% after 100 hours for TET, 122 hours for CIP, 212 hours for SDZ and 240 hours for SMX. Nevertheless, the removal of all antibiotics via photocatalysis was around 99 - 100% after 4.2 hours for TET, 3.5 hours for CIP, 7.1 hours for SDZ and 16.5 hours for SMX. The photolysis for the four veterinary antibiotics followed a first-order irreversible kinetic model. The photocatalysis of TET, CIP and SDZ followed a Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetic model, and adsorption was

considered the limiting step. SMX followed a first-order irreversible kinetic model. The photolytic degradation rate constant (k_1) was 0.00073 min^{-1} for TET, 0.00055 min^{-1} for CIP, 0.00031 min^{-1} for SDZ and 0.00027 min^{-1} for SMX. While for photocatalysis k_1 was 0.0044 min^{-1} for SMX; k_{L-H} was 0.0284 min^{-1} for TET, 0.0379 min^{-1} for CIP and 0.0141 min^{-1} for SDZ. The VA degradation was enhanced by the use of a catalyst. Additionally, electrical energy per order (E_{EO}) was assessed to estimate the electrical energy efficiency of each process. E_{EO} values for photolysis were $339.06 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for TET, $449.84 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for CIP, $795.31 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for SDZ and $897.71 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for SMX. On the other hand, E_{EO} values for photocatalysis were $14.96 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for TET, $12.07 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for CIP, $20.39 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for SDZ and $62.10 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for SMX. The energy consumption for photocatalysis was considerably lower than for photolysis. This study showed, when working with a pH of 8 (a typical pH from wastewater from livestock farms) and a VA mixture whose concentrations resemble the characteristics of real water samples, that photolysis and photocatalysis are potential processes for wastewater treatment with low energy consumption.

Keywords: Photodegradation; AOPs, E_{EO} ; TiO_2 ; UVC

1. Introduction

Antibiotics are one of the most important pharmaceutical groups used by humans and are also used in veterinary medicine and aquaculture. Veterinary antibiotics (VA) are widely used to increase animal production and prevent, control or treat diseases [1,2]. The widespread use of antibiotics means that they are commonly found in wastewater, surface water, ground water, and drinking water at trace concentration levels, ranging from ng/L to mg/L. The presence of VA in aquatic environments has become an

increasing global concern due to their potential adverse effects to the environment and significant public health implications [3].

Treatment technologies available for VA include biological processes and/or physical or chemical treatments. Biological processes which use aerobic or anaerobic sludge [4], microalgae [5], algal-bacterial consortium [6], among others, are cost-efficient; however, some VA can inhibit the regular function of microbial populations due to their toxicity and microbial growth resistance. On the other hand, chemical process such as coagulation [7] or ion exchange [8] present low efficiency, high cost, and secondary pollution issues. Similarly, physical processes such as activated carbon [9] cannot eliminate VA since they only transfer the pollutants from one phase to another [10].

The growing interest in VA has led to extensive studies on environmentally friendly processes which can be cost effective. Over the last few years, ultraviolet (UV) irradiation has demonstrated its effectiveness for chemical oxidation and water and wastewater disinfection. Direct and natural photolytic decomposition and transformation of many organic pollutants has been proved [11]. Moreover, photocatalysis has emerged as a promising technique for VA removal as it can mineralize a variety of recalcitrant organics through the generation of hydroxyl radical (OH^{\bullet}) which is highly reactive and non-selective [12]. Titanium dioxide (TiO_2) is the most widely used catalyst due to its abundance, photo stability, good performance and non-toxic characteristics [13].

Photocatalytic processes have shown to be a suitable choice because they can obtain high mineralization percentages. However, most of the previous studies found in the literature have focused on a single contaminant which may not be representative of real water treatment conditions [14]. From this perspective, the aim of this study is to

determine the photolytic and photocatalytic degradation of a mixture of TET, CIP, SDZ and SMX, as representative compounds of fluoroquinolones, sulfonamides and tetracyclines, the three antibiotic families most frequently found in water samples, at small concentrations similar to those found in real samples.

To determine the influence of the initial concentration on the photolytic (UVC) and photocatalytic (UVC/TiO₂) degradation of TET, CIP, SDZ and SMX, four different initial concentrations (20, 100, 500 and 1000 µg/L) of each compound were used. These concentrations were selected to resemble a range of VA concentrations in manure which can be found in the literature (sulfonamides 6.99-5650 µg/kg, fluoroquinolones 63.63-5567 µg/kg, and tetracyclines 6.20-290.5 µg/kg [15]). Removals, kinetics and energy consumption were studied and compared with the literature. Other important parameters which can influence the efficiency of the process – such as pH, light intensity, type of radiation, use of O₂, and irradiation time – remained unchanged during the operation time. However, they were considered in the comparison with the literature.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Individual stock solutions of 1 g/L for TET, SDZ and SMX were prepared on a weight basis in methanol (MeOH). CIP was dissolved in H₂O/MeOH (1:1) containing 0.2% v/v hydrochloric acid (HCl). MeOH of high analytical grade was acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Stockholm, Sweden), VA of high purity grade (N95%) and HCl (37%) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Tres Cantos, Madrid, Spain). CIP, SDZ and SMX were acquired as neutral non-solvated molecules and TET was purchased as a hydrochloride. P-25 titanium dioxide (Degussa AG, Germany) was supplied by Quimidroga S.A. TiO₂ specific surface was 50 ± 15 m², the particle size was 21 nm and

the bandwidth energy was 3.2 eV. Ultrapure water was generated by a Milli-Q (MQ) Advantage Ultrapure Water purification system and filtered through a 0.22 μm Millipak Express membrane and an LC-Pak polishing unit by Merck Millipore (Billerica, MA, USA).

2.2. Experimental set-up

Fig. 1. Photoreactor system scheme.

The photoreactor system (Fig.1) consists of a methacrylate reactor formed by two concentric tubes. The outer tube has an inner diameter of 14 cm and the inner tube has an outer diameter of 6 cm. These measurements have been designed so that the wall of the inner tube to the outside does not exceed 4 cm in order to avoid loss of radiant energy. The active zone in the reactor is delimited by the two tubes and the liquid level, which has a useful volume of 5.6 L. Philips UVC lamp (TUV PL-L 36W/4P 1CT/25) with a peak emission at 257.7 nm and TiO_2 in suspension were used. A homogeneous incident

flux of 13.33 mW/cm² was used. A cylindrical shape diffuser placed at the bottom of the reactor, which injected air from a diaphragm pump, was used for a continuous mixing.

2.3. Degradation analysis

Photolytic and photocatalytic degradation experiments were performed under UVC irradiation at 25 °C and a pH of 8.0. Tests were performed with a mixture of four antibiotics to a final concentration of 1000, 500, 100 and 20 µg/L per antibiotic. After filling the reactor, for the photolytic analysis, an initial sample was taken to determine the initial antibiotic concentration and the UVC lamp was immediately turned on. For the photocatalytic analysis, an initial sample was taken to determine the initial antibiotic concentration. After that, TiO₂ was added to the reactor under continuous mixing to obtain a concentration of 1 g/L. The solution was stirred under dark conditions for 30 min and two samples were taken every 15 min. Once the adsorption equilibrium was reached (which according to literature was reached at 30 minutes [1,13,16]), the UVC lamp was turned on and samples were taken at prefixed intervals, filtered through 0.22 mm pore-size nylon syringe filters (Fisherbrand) and stored at 4 °C before analysis. Experiments were conducted in triplicate.

2.4. Analytical method

The quantitative determination of selected antibiotics was carried out by ultra-high performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) coupled to a MS/MS spectrometry. The chromatographic separation was carried out using an Exion LC AD instrument from AB Sciex (Framingham, MA, USA) and a reversed-phase column EVO C18 (50 × 2.1 i.d. mm, 1.7 µm particle size) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). MS/MS analysis was performed by a triple quadrupole 6500+ from AB Sciex in selected reaction

monitoring (SRM) mode. The procedure was based on the one previously developed by López-Serna et al. [17], employing direct injection of the (diluted) samples, without any pre-concentration step.

2.5. Zero-point charge (ZPC)

pH plays a significant role in VA photocatalytic degradation in regards to the surface charge properties of the catalyst, the size of the catalyst aggregates, the adsorption of VA on the catalyst surface, the ionic forms of the VA, and hydrophobicity [10,12,18]. Regarding to the surface charge properties and the particle size of the catalyst, the pH_{ZPC} is the pH at which the catalyst surface is globally neutral; consequently, the electrostatic attraction between the photocatalyst particles and the VA is minimal. Above the zero-point charge (ZPC) value, the catalyst surface will be negatively charged and will repel the negatively charged VA. Below the ZPC value, the catalyst surface will be positively charged and will exert an electrostatic force towards the anionic compounds.

To calculate pH_{ZPC} , 50 mL of Milli-Q water were taken in 100 mL glass beakers, adjusting the pH between 3 and 11 by adding the appropriate amount of 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH. After that, 0.5 g of TiO_2 were added to each glass beaker, and the final pH values were measured after 48 hours under stirring at room temperature. The values of the final pH were plotted versus the initial pH. The pH_{ZPC} corresponds to the point where the curve of the final pH versus the initial pH cuts the graph diagonally [19].

2.6. Kinetic analysis

Four kinetic models – zero-order (Eq. 1), pseudo-first order irreversible (Eq. 2), pseudo-first order reversible (Eq. 3) and Langmuir-Hinshelwood (Eq. 4) – were used to fit the experimental data.

$$r = -\frac{dC}{dt} = k_0 \quad (1)$$

$$r = -\frac{dC}{dt} = k_1 \cdot C \quad (2)$$

$$r = -\frac{dC}{dt} = k_2 \cdot (C - C_e) \quad (3)$$

$$r = -\frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{k_r \cdot K \cdot C}{1 + K \cdot C} \quad (4)$$

where, r is the rate of antibiotics degradation ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), C is the concentration at any time ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), C_e is the concentration at equilibrium ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), k_0 is the zero-order rate constant ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$), k_1 is the pseudo-first order irreversible rate constant (min^{-1}), k_2 is the pseudo-first order reversible rate constant (min^{-1}), and k_r ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and K ($\text{L}\cdot\mu\text{g}^{-1}$) are the rate constant and the adsorption constant, respectively.

Integrating Eq. (1), (2), (3) and (4) with respect to the limits $C = C_0$ (C_0 is the initial antibiotic concentration before irradiation and after 30 min to reach the adsorption equilibrium when TiO_2 is used) and $C = C_t$ (C_t is the antibiotic concentration at time t (min) under light irradiation), Eq. (5), (6), (7) and (8) can be obtained:

$$C_t = C_0 - k_0 \cdot t \quad (5)$$

$$C_t = C_0 \cdot e^{-k_1 \cdot t} \quad (6)$$

$$C_t = C_e + (C_0 - C_e) \cdot e^{-k_2 \cdot t} \quad (7)$$

$$-\ln\left(\frac{C_t}{C_0}\right) - K \cdot (C_t - C_0) = k_r \cdot K \cdot t \quad (8)$$

Eq. (6) is a particular solution of Eq. (7) when $C_e = 0$; thus, the pseudo-first order kinetics is not reversible.

2.7. Electrical energy determination

In order to compare photocatalysis by means of energy consumption with other advanced oxidation processes (AOP), the electrical energy per order (E_{EO}) was calculated. E_{EO} is defined as the electrical energy required to reduce the concentration of a pollutant by one order of magnitude (90%) in a fixed volume of polluted water. E_{EO} is calculated as follows:

$$E_{EO} = \frac{P \cdot t}{V \cdot \log\left(\frac{C_0}{C_f}\right)} \quad (9)$$

where, P is the rated power (kW) of the AOP system, V is the volume (m^3) of water treated in the time t (h), C_0 ($\mu g/L$) is the initial antibiotic concentration before irradiation (and after 30 min to reach the adsorption equilibrium when TiO_2 is used), and C_f ($\mu g \cdot L^{-1}$) is the final antibiotic concentration.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Zero-point charge (ZPC)

Several authors have reported the ZPC of TiO_2 in the pH range of 4.5 to 7.0 [18]. In the present study, pH_{ZPC} for TiO_2 was found at pH 6.4 (Fig. 2). Therefore, since the present study was performed at pH 8 to resemble pH of real water samples, the photocatalyst was negatively charged.

Fig. 2. Evaluation of zero-point charge (pH_{zpc}) for TiO_2 .

Considering the pH of the solution, the VA pK_a , and the pH_{ZPC} of TiO_2 , the following predictions of the different interaction mechanisms can be made. The four antibiotics used in the present study can exist as three different species (ionic, cationic and zwitterionic) over a broader pH range. TET with $\text{pK}_{a1} = 3.32$ and $\text{pK}_{a2} = 9.58$ will be in its zwitterionic form and present hydrophobic interactions with the photocatalyst that will be negatively charged [20]. CIP pK_a is 6.09 for the carboxylic acid group and 8.74 for the nitrogen on the piperazinyll ring. The acid will be dissociated at pH values higher than 6.3, and the nitrogen will be protonated at pH values lower than 8.7. At pH 8.0, CIP will be dissociated in anions and cations. Through electrostatic attraction, cations will be adsorbed on the negatively charged TiO_2 [21]. SDZ pK_a is 6.36 and SMX pK_a values are $\text{pK}_{a1} = 1.6$ and $\text{pK}_{a2} = 5.7$. At pH 8.0, SDZ and SMX ($\text{pH} > \text{pK}_a$; $\text{pH}_{\text{PZC}} < \text{pH}$) will be negatively charged which will cause an electrostatic repulsion with negatively charged TiO_2 [20].

3.2. Degradation of veterinary antibiotics

To the best of our knowledge, for the first time, a mixture of four antibiotics with an initial concentration range adjusted to those that can be found in real water samples was used to analyze the degradation of VA via photolysis and photocatalysis. VA photolysis was studied in batch experiments for 180 min (Fig. 3A-3D). For the four antibiotics, a decrease in the initial concentration over time was observed. In all the studied conditions, TET showed a higher decrease in its initial concentration because it is a very light sensitive antibiotic. In a literature review, Prakash et al., [22] compared the photolysis of tetracyclines, quinolones and sulfonamides, and showed that tetracyclines can obtain high removals, around 80%, while quinolones and sulfonamides achieve very low removals.

Fig. 3. Antibiotic removal by photolysis (A) 1000, (B) 500, (C) 100, and (D) 20 µgL⁻¹ initial concentration. Error bars represent ± standard error of the mean.

Moreover, photocatalysis was evaluated for 180 min (Fig. 4A - 4D). Starting with an initial VA concentration of 100 µg/L before adsorption, complete removal of TET was obtained at 180 min and at 90 min CIP was totally removed (Fig. 4C). At 20 µg/L before adsorption, complete removal of TET and CIP was obtained at 75 and 60 min, respectively (Fig. 4D). In all the studied conditions, CIP showed the highest decrease in its initial concentration. Considering the pH_{ZPC} and pH solution, CIP was dissociated – hence its cations enhanced its adsorption capacity on the negatively charged TiO_2 through electrostatic attraction [23]. Adsorption into the catalyst is crucial to obtain high removal percentages. In the following sections, we will determine the kinetics of the photolytic and photocatalytic processes as well as the removal percentages than can be obtained by these processes.

Fig. 4. Antibiotic removal by photocatalysis (A) 1000, (B) 500, (C) 100, and (D) 20 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ initial concentration. Error bars represent \pm standard error of the mean.

3.3. Kinetics of degradation of veterinary antibiotics

The photolysis and photocatalysis of the four veterinary antibiotics were investigated with zero-order and pseudo-first order kinetic models. A pseudo-first order kinetic model was evaluated and considered both an irreversible and a reversible reaction. It was considered that the photolytic and the photocatalytic reaction could reach an equilibrium where parental compounds and byproducts generated during the process would compete for the photons, electron holes produced on the catalyst and/or the generated oxidation species. Additionally, the Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetic model, which considered adsorption as the limiting step, was used to study the kinetics of photocatalysis. To calculate the kinetic parameters of photocatalysis, the experimental data was considered after adsorption when the UVC light was turned on.

The kinetic parameters were obtained as follows (Table 1):

1. An adjustment of the experimental data to a zero-order kinetic was done as shown in Eq. (5) by drawing the concentration data versus time. If the kinetics is a zero-order, then the experimental data will fit to a straight line with the ordinate at the origin C_0 and slope $-k_0$.
2. Analogously transforming Eq. (6), Eq. (9) is obtained:

$$-\ln\left(\frac{C_t}{C_0}\right) = k_1 \cdot t \quad (9)$$

By drawing $-\ln(C_t/C_0)$ versus t , if the kinetics is a pseudo-first order irreversible, then the experimental data will fit to a straight line with the ordinate at the origin C_0 and slope k_1 .

3. The experimental data was also fitted to a pseudo-first order reversible kinetics by transforming Eq. (7) into:

$$-\ln \left[\frac{C_t - C_e}{C_0 - C_e} \right] = k_2 \cdot t \quad (10)$$

By drawing $-\ln [(C_t - C_e)/(C_0 - C_e)]$ versus t , if the kinetics is a pseudo-first order reversible, then the experimental data will fit to a straight line with the ordinate at the origin and slope k_2 . For this, we must find the values of parameters k_2 and C_e which would make the experimental data fit best to that straight line. Those parameters were obtained by the GRG Nonlinear Solving method.

4. Fitting experimental data of photolysis and photocatalysis as in step 3, the C_e obtained was 0, it means that the kinetic model that best fit was the pseudo-first order irreversible model.
5. Additionally, for photocatalysis, when the experimental data was fitted to a pseudo-first order irreversible kinetic model at small antibiotic concentrations, the experimental data started to disperse from the line. Therefore, we inferred that the photocatalysis of the antibiotic might be limited by the adsorption of the antibiotics into the catalyst and that the photocatalytic process might follow a Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetics [20, 35].

Once again, the best values of the constants k_r and K in Eq. (8) were obtained using the GRG Nonlinear Solving method.

6. The coefficient of determination R^2 was used to decide whether the experimental data better fit a zero-order, pseudo-first order irreversible/reversible, or Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetics model.

3.3.1. Photolysis

Pseudo-first order irreversible kinetics presented R^2 values closer to unity and fit best to the experimental data for the photolysis of TET, CIP, SDZ and SMX (Fig. 5). TET and CIP were degraded faster than SDZ and SMX. TET presented the higher rate constant in the photolytic process. The pseudo-first order irreversible rate constant for the removal of antibiotics by photolysis were 0.00073 min^{-1} for TET, 0.00055 min^{-1} for CIP, 0.00031 min^{-1} for SDZ and 0.00027 min^{-1} for SMX.

Fig. 5. (A) Linear representation of pseudo-first order kinetics for the antibiotic removal by photolysis. (B) Antibiotic concentration variation by photolysis along time. Error bars represent \pm standard error of the mean.

A comparative analysis of the rate constants previously reported in the literature for TET, CIP, SDZ and SMX degradation by photolysis showed that the results obtained in the present study are comparable to those reported by other authors (Table 2). Wu et al. [16] reported negligible photolysis of TET using UV irradiation. Yun et al. [26] found higher photolytic rate constants ($0.0045 - 0.0014 \text{ min}^{-1}$) than the ones obtained in the present study, despite its higher initial TET concentration and its lower UV light intensity. The light source was not specified so no further comparison can be made. Li and Hu, [27] obtained a k_1 value of 0.01 min^{-1} for photolytic degradation which was higher than the k_1 value obtained in the present study (0.00073 min^{-1}). The reactor used by Li and Hu, [27] was a 100 mm x 50 mm dish which allows for easier light irradiation into the solution.

In another study, Li and Hu, [28] obtained higher rate constants for CIP removal than the ones obtained in the present study (0.0005 min^{-1}), due to the reactor design used by Li and Hu, [28] which was shorter and the separation of the reactor surface with the lights was 2 cm. Salma et al. [29] reported a higher rate constant of 0.002 min^{-1} for photolysis by using UVC light, as we did in the present study, but the irradiance was not specified. Triquet et al. [30] achieved a higher rate constant of 0.003 min^{-1} for photolysis, but the UV type was not specified so no further comparison can be made. Nevertheless, the present results corroborate what Triquet et al. [30] stated which was that CIP could be degraded by both techniques, photolysis and photocatalysis, with faster kinetics while using a photocatalyst.

Loureiro dos Louros et al. [31] studied the photodegradation of SDZ by UVC light, obtaining a rate constant of 0.002 min^{-1} which was higher than that obtained in the present study k_1 (0.00031 min^{-1}). This is because Loureiro dos Louros et al. [31] used tubes with small internal diameters as reactors which facilitates the light irradiation into the solution. Li et al. [32] obtaining a higher rate constant (0.02 min^{-1}) than the one obtained in the present study for photolysis degradation of SDZ due to the use of a lower pH; they determined that the higher the acidity, the greater the rate constant. Yadav et al. [33] analyzed the degradation of SDZ, achieving a photolysis rate constant of 0.001 min^{-1} which was higher than the one obtained in the present study; UVC light was used too, but the light irradiation and pH conditions were not specified.

Wang et al. [34] studied the photolytic degradation of SMX and obtained a k_1 value of 0.002 min^{-1} which was higher than the one obtained in the present study (0.00027 min^{-1}) due to the use of a high sunlight irradiance. Additionally, Yuan et al. [35] studied the degradation of SMX under UVC irradiation and achieved a higher k_1 value of 0.03

min^{-1} due to the photocatalytic system used, which were small dishes with a high surface area and a small depth, allowing for better light irradiation into the solution.

3.3.2. Photocatalysis

The Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetics model best fit to the experimental data for the photocatalysis of TET, CIP and SDZ (Fig. 6). CIP had the highest rate constants of the four antibiotics. CIP removal was faster than the other three antibiotics in photocatalysis due to its better absorption into the catalyst; the $\log K_{ow}$ of CIP (1.32) was higher than that of TET (-1.37), SDZ (-0.09) and SMX (0.89), indicating that CIP has a better affinity to TiO_2 . When applying the Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetics model to SMX, the K (constant for adsorption) obtained was 0, which means that SMX photocatalysis was not limited by adsorption. SMX followed a first-order irreversible kinetic model with a k_1 of 0.0044 min^{-1} .

Fig. 6. Linear representation of Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetics for the antibiotic removal by photocatalysis. (B) Antibiotic concentration variation by photocatalysis along time. Error bars represent \pm standard error of the mean.

* Photocatalysis of SMX adjusted to a pseudo-first order kinetics because $K=0$

** The linear adjust corresponds to a pseudo-first order kinetics because $K=0$

Several researchers have simplified the Langmuir-Hinshelwood model by considering the term $K \cdot C \ll 1$. Thus, the model can be simplified and takes the form of a pseudo-first order kinetics. From Table 1, k_r from the Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetics has different units than k_1 from a pseudo-first order kinetics. Thus, it is not appropriate to approximate Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetics to a pseudo-first order model as reported in the literature [25,30]. However, the product of $k_r \cdot K$ gives a constant k_{L-H} with the same units (min^{-1}) of a pseudo-first order kinetic, which we will use for comparison purposes. In this respect, k_{L-H} for the removal of antibiotics by photocatalysis was 0.0284 min^{-1} for TET, 0.0379 min^{-1} for CIP and 0.0141 min^{-1} for SDZ.

Wu et al. [16] reported photocatalytic rate constants of $0.02 - 0.04 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for TET degradation, similar to the one obtained in this study (0.0284 min^{-1}). Li and Hu, [27] obtained a higher k_1 value of 0.1 min^{-1} due to the pH of the solution. According to the pH_{ZPC} of TiO_2 , the catalyst is positively charged under pH 6.4 and negatively charged above pH 6.4 [36]. Since in the present study the pH was 8, TET will be negatively charged and thus there will be electron repulsion with the catalyst. Furthermore, Li and Hu, [27] showed that by using a pH of 6 that TET will be in its zwitterion form and therefore a better adsorption between the antibiotic and the catalyst will improve photocatalytic degradation [37].

Li and Hu, [28] obtained higher rate constants for CIP removal of 0.22 min^{-1} than the one obtained in the present study (0.0379 min^{-1}) by using UVA light. Salma et al. [29] reported a smaller rate constant of 0.006 min^{-1} using UVC because they used a pH of 3. At pH 3, according to the pH_{ZPC} of TiO_2 and pKa of CIP, CIP and TiO_2 will be positively charged and there will be electrostatic repulsion between them. Triquet et al. [30] achieved a higher rate constant of 0.06 min^{-1} for CIP photocatalysis because a small narrow reactor was used which facilitates the light irradiation into the solution.

For SDZ removal, Yadav et al. [33] achieved a photocatalysis rate constant of 0.01 min^{-1} like the one obtained in the present study (0.0141 min^{-1}). It is important to mention that the rate constants of the antibiotics in the current study might be enhanced by the use of air for mixing the solution; dissolved oxygen (DO) trap photogenerated electrons, prevent charge carrier recombination, act as an electron scavenger and enable the formation of superoxide and reactive oxygen species (ROS) [18,38].

Yuan et al. [35] achieved k_1 values of 0.1 to 0.5 min^{-1} for photocatalysis degradation of SMX while using 0.4 to 1.6 g/L TiO_2 photocatalysis. The higher rate

constants obtained by Yuan et al. [35] than the one obtained in the present study (0.0044 min^{-1}) can be explained by the pH difference. According to SMX pKa values, when the solution pH is higher than 5.6, SMX will be in its anionic form, while when the pH is between 1.85 and 5.6, SMX will be in its neutral form. Boreen et al. [39] stated that the neutral, rather than the anionic form, is the most photodegradable state. At the neutral state, SMX could obtain stronger light adsorption, corresponding to higher photochemical reactivity. Thus, the decomposition rate will decrease as the pH increases [13, 40, 44].

3.4. Removal of veterinary antibiotics

The removal of the four veterinary antibiotics by photolysis is shown in Fig. 5B, while their removal by photocatalysis can be seen in Fig. 6B. TET removal by photolysis was 99% after 100 h and TET removal by photocatalysis was 99.75% after 4.2 h. Wu et al. [16] studied the degradation of 10 mg/L of TET with a 20 mW/cm^2 visible light irradiation. After 150 min, no photolysis was observed. However, while using 0.2 g/L TiO_2 , 76.6% removal was obtained. Moreover, when UV instead of visible light was used for the photocatalysis process, 94.8% of TET was removed. Safari et al. [40], using an initial concentration of 1 g/L TiO_2 , 55 mg/L TET and 2.5 mW/cm^2 UV irradiation, achieved 23.8% and 83.2% for photolysis and photocatalysis degradation, respectively. Oseghe and Ofomaja, [41] investigated the degradation of 5 mg/L TET under 4.6 mW/cm^2 visible white LED light irradiation, attaining 26% photolysis and 40% photocatalysis removal. Comparing these reviewed studies with the results obtained in the present study, the findings agree on the capacity of photolysis and photocatalysis to degrade TET, with enhanced degradation when using a catalyst and UV irradiation.

CIP removal by photolysis was 98.7% after 122 h and CIP removal by photocatalysis was 99.90% after 3.5 h. Other studies have reported the same trend for CIP

as the ones observed in the present study; photo degradation by UV irradiation and complete removal of CIP by the use of TiO₂ powder. Mondal et al., [42] achieved 60% removal of 10 mg/L CIP by UVC irradiation after 120 min. Salma et al., [29] found a photolytic and photocatalytic removal of 33% and 58%, respectively, for 0.02 µg/L CIP under UVC irradiation. Triquet et al., [30] by using 10 mW/cm² UV irradiation for the degradation of 20 mg/L CIP, obtained a complete removal of CIP after 8 h by photolysis and 1 h by photocatalysis.

SDZ removal by photolysis was 98.1% after 212 h and SDZ removal by photocatalysis was 99.61% after 7.1 h. The results for SDZ are consistent with previous findings in the literature; SDZ proved to be photosensitive and higher degradation can be obtained by photocatalysis. Loureiro dos Louros et al. [31] reached 100% removal of 500 µg/L SDZ after 36 h of UV photolysis, and after 5 h of operation, the removal was around 25%. Yadav et al. [33] used UVC irradiation for the removal of 1 mg/L SDZ, obtaining 20% removal by photolysis after 180 min, and 55% removal by photocatalysis after 120 min. Li et al. [32] used UV irradiation for the removal of 1.5 mg/L SDZ, obtaining 95% removal after 150 min.

SMX removal by photolysis was 98.2% after 240 h and SMX removal by photocatalysis was 98.84% after 16.5 h. The SMX results are comparable with those from the literature; photolysis and photocatalysis demonstrated their ability to degrade SMX, with a higher removal when using TiO₂. Alharbi et al. [43] studied the degradation of 5 mg/L SMX, obtaining a complete removal after 8 min under 1.04 W/cm² UV irradiation. For the degradation of 200 µg/L SMX, Yuan et al. [35] achieved 53.6 to 91% removal by using 0.4 to 1.6 g/L TiO₂ under 0.5 mW/cm² UVC irradiation after 16 min. Cai and Hu, [2] analyzed the degradation of 400 µg/L SMX using $4.32 \cdot 10^3$ mWs/cm² UV energy

irradiation, and reached 16% removal by photolysis and 91% removal by photocatalysis with 0.05 g/L TiO₂ and pH 5.6 after 20 min.

3.5. Energy consumption

The electrical energy consumption for the photolytic and photocatalytic degradation of the veterinary antibiotics was calculated. The E_{EO} values for photolysis were 339.06 kWh/m³/order for TET, 449.84 kWh/m³/order for CIP, 795.31 kWh/m³/order for SDZ, and 897.71 kWh/m³/order for SMX. SMX turned out to be the antibiotic which consumed more energy for its degradation. Likewise, for the photocatalytic process, SMX presented the highest E_{EO} value. The E_{EO} values for photocatalysis were 14.96 kWh/m³/order for TET, 12.07 kWh/m³/order for CIP, 20.39 kWh/m³/order for SDZ, and 62.10 kWh/m³/order for SMX. The faster photolysis rate of TET and the higher photocatalytic rate of CIP means that they are the antibiotics with the lowest electrical energy consumption in each process. E_{EO} values for photolysis were around 15 to 37 times higher than the E_{EO} values for photocatalysis.

A literature review of E_{EO} for the degradation of TET, CIP, SDZ and SMX displayed a diverse range of values (Table 3). Yao et al. [44] evaluated the photodegradation of TET using 41.8 mW/cm² UV irradiation, obtaining an E_{EO} value of 8.65 kWh/m³/order. Yao et al. [44] obtained a higher rate constant than the one obtained in the present study by applying a light irradiation which was three times higher. Nevertheless, the E_{EO} was smaller which might be due to the type of reactor used by Yao et al. [44]. Yao et al. [44] used a mini-fluidic VUV/UV photoreaction system (MVPS), which has a high transmittance of UV light and a small distance from the lamp surface to the reaction solution.

Hassani et al. [45] studied the degradation of 20 mg/L CIP, obtaining a 0.0006 min^{-1} reaction rate constant and $2048 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order } E_{EO}$ for photo-degradation (UV) after 120 min, and a 0.0063 min^{-1} reaction rate constant and $195.1 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order } E_{EO}$ for photocatalysis with TiO_2 . Lower energy consumptions were obtained in the present study. Yet the results demonstrate that UVC photocatalysis has a better performance and a lower energy consumption than photolysis. E_{EO} is proportional to the inverse of the reaction constant. Therefore, as photocatalysis has higher k_1 values than photolysis, the E_{EO} values are lower. Additionally, Hassani et al. [45] made a comparison in the use of UVA, UVB and UVC, revealing that UVC photogeneration of e^-/h^+ pairs is high which will generate more reactive radicals for the degradation of contaminants.

For the photo-degradation of SDZ, Yadav et al. [33] acquired a 0.001 min^{-1} reaction rate and $922 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order } E_{EO}$ while the present study obtained lower a E_{EO} value of $795.31 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$. The difference can be explained by the use of a different rated power in the two studies. Yadav et al. [33] used 56 W while present study used 36 W. Moreover, for the photocatalytic degradation of SDZ with TiO_2 , Yadav et al. [33] obtained a 0.006 min^{-1} reaction rate and $138 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order } E_{EO}$. The present study obtained a lower E_{EO} value of $29.79 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ due to the higher reaction rate obtained (0.0141 min^{-1}). In addition, the current study used a larger reactor volume of 5.6 L while the reactor volume used in Yadav et al. [33] was of 2 L.

Kim et al. [46] obtained an E_{EO} value of $150 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for the UVC degradation of 30 mg/L SMX at pH 4.63. Luo et al. [47] calculated an E_{EO} value of $0.0023 \text{ kWh/m}^3/\text{order}$ for the UV degradation of 5 mg/L SMX. There is a significant difference between the energy consumption values reported in the literature. However, when compared with the results obtained in the present study, UVC photocatalysis with TiO_2

demonstrated its potential as a good option for SMX removal from wastewater as it can attain high removals with a low energy consumption.

In addition, UVC photolysis and UVC/TiO₂ photocatalysis energy consumption for the degradation of SDZ and SMX obtained in the present study is comparable with other AOP studies. Yadav et al. [33] presented the E_{EO} values for the degradation of SDZ with different AOPs such as oxidation with persulfate (127.9 kWh/m³/order), photo-oxidation with persulfate (1.72 kWh/m³/order), and photocatalysis with TiO₂ supported in granular activated carbon (34.5 kWh/m³/order). Kim et al. [46] obtained a 0.46 kWh/m³/order for water radiolysis by gamma rays and 27.53 kWh/m³/order for ozone. Even though gamma rays have a low energy consumption, their potential use at industrial scale might not be feasible. Mirzaei et al. [48] evaluated the photocatalytic degradation of SMX by ZnO in the presence of fluoride ions by 10 W UVC irradiation, obtaining a rate constant of 0.099 min⁻¹ and a 3.88 kWh/m³/order E_{EO}. These comparisons show that photo-degradation (UVC) and photocatalysis with TiO₂ (UVC/TiO₂) are promising techniques for VA removal.

4. Conclusions

Removal efficiencies, kinetics and energy consumption were evaluated for the photo-degradation (UVC) and photocatalytic-degradation with TiO₂ (UVC/TiO₂) of a mixture of four antibiotics at different initial concentrations. TET, CIP, SDZ and SMX proved to be photosensitive and capable of being removed by either photolysis or photocatalysis. Photocatalysis attained the higher degradation percentages. The photolysis for the four veterinary antibiotics followed a first-order irreversible kinetic model. The photocatalysis of TET, CIP and SDZ followed a Langmuir-Hinshelwood kinetic model, and adsorption was considered as the limiting step. SMX followed a first-

order irreversible kinetic model. The calculation of the electrical energy consumed by both processes showed that photocatalysis is energy efficient compared with other systems. These results are helpful to assess the extent of degradation of VAs in water treatment processes by photolysis and photocatalysis. UVC photocatalysis with TiO₂ was found to be efficient and cost-effective in the removal of VAs. Further investigations shall be done in the influence of different parameters such as ions and oxidants present in real water samples that could enhance the photolytic and photocatalytic degradation of VAs.

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Table 1. Kinetic parameters for the photolysis and photocatalysis of veterinary antibiotics.

Compound	Photolysis									Photocatalysis									
	C ₀ (µg/L)	Zero Order		First Order					C ₀ (µg/L)	Zero Order		First Order					Langmuir-Hinshelwood		
		k ₀ (min ⁻¹)	R ² (-)	Irreversible		Reversible*				k ₀ (min ⁻¹)	R ² (-)	Irreversible		Reversible*			k _r (µg·L ⁻¹ ·min ⁻¹)	K (L·µg ⁻¹)	R ² (-)
			k ₁ (min ⁻¹)	R ² (-)	C _e (µg/L)	k ₂ (min ⁻¹)	R ² (-)			k ₁ (min ⁻¹)	R ² (-)	C _e (µg/L)	k ₂ (min ⁻¹)	R ² (-)					
TET	1000	0.199	0.79	0.00073	0.99	0	0.00073	0.99	710	3.781	0.82	0.0148	0.99	0	0.015	0.99	11.137	0.00255	0.98
CIP	1000	0.162	0.82	0.00055	0.99	0	0.00055	0.99	771	2.781	0.77	0.0194	0.98	0	0.019	0.98	15.040	0.00252	0.97
SDZ	1000	0.092	0.59	0.00031	0.99	0	0.00031	0.99	927	2.908	0.79	0.0089	0.98	0	0.009	0.98	19.776	0.000713	0.98
SMX	1000	0.082	0.83	0.00027	0.99	0	0.00027	0.99	946	1.113	0.86	0.0044	0.99	0.02	0.005	0.96	---	0	---

* Reversibility is not detected (C_e=0)

Table 2. Comparative review from the last five years on the application of photolysis and photocatalysis with TiO₂ for the removal of VA

TiO ₂	Contaminant	Irradiance or lamp power	Light source	Irradiation Time	Rate constant (min ⁻¹)	pH	References
0.2 g/L	10 mg/L TET	20 mW/cm ²	UV	120 min	0.02 – 0.04	-	Wu et al. [16]
0	10 - 40 mg/L TET	1.45 mW/cm ²	UV	15 days	0.0045 – 0.0014	6.2	Yun et al. [26]
0 0.002 g/L	500 µg/L TET	4 mW/cm ²	UVA/LED	30 min	0.01 0.1	6	Li and Hu, [27]
0 0.1 g/L	20 mg/L CIP	10 mW/cm ²	UVA/LED	60 min	0.01 0.22	6	Li and Hu, [28]
0 20.5 g/m ² glass plate	0.02 µg/L CIP	15 W	UVC	120 min	0.002 0.006	3	Salma et al. [29]
0 0.12 g/L	20 mg/L CIP	10 mW/cm ²	UV	8 hours 1 hour	0.003 0.06	-	Triquet et al. [30]
0	500 µg/L SDZ	5.5 mW/cm ²	UVC	36 hours	0.002	7.3	Loureiro dos Louros et al. [31]
0	1.5 mg/L SDZ	350 W	UV	150 min	0.02	7	Li et al. [32]
0 1 g/L	1 mg/L SDZ	28 W	UVC	120 min	0.001 0.01	-	Yadav et al. [33]
0.05 g/L	400 µg/L SMX	4.32·10 ³ mWs/cm ²	UV	20 min	-	5.6	Cai and Hu, [2]
0	150 µg/L SMX	983 mW/cm ²	Solar simulator	4 hours	0.002	8	Wang et al. [34]

0						0.03		
0.4 g/L	200 µg/L SMX	0.5 mW/cm ²	UVC	16 min		0.1	6	Yuan et al. [35]
1.6 g/L						0.5		

Table 3. Comparative review of the energy consumed for VA removal by photolysis and photocatalysis with TiO₂

TiO ₂ (g/L)	Contaminant	Irradiance or lamp power	Light source	Irradiation Time	E _{EO} (kWh/m ³ /order)	pH	Rate constant (min ⁻¹)	References
0	8.9 mg/L TET	41.8 mW/cm ²	UV	12 min	8.65	7	0.0098	Yao et al. [44]
0 0.1	20 mg/L CIP	16 W	UV	120 min	2048 195.1	5	0.0006 0.0063	Hassani et al. [45]
0 1	1 mg/L SDZ	56 W 28 W	UVC	240 min 120 min	922.22 138	-	0.001 0.006	Yadav et al. [33]
0	30 mg/L SMX	6 W	UVC	15 min	1.5	4.63	-	Kim et al. [46]
0	5 mg/L SMX	10 W	UV	15 min	0.0023	8	0.36	Luo et al. [47]